

Assessing the impact of inhibitors on the viability of biological samples for forensic DNA analysis: A pilot study

ADEYANJU MOSURO^a, SHARLIZE PEDROZA-MATUTE^{a,b}, STEVE CUMMINGS^b,
TASNIM MUNSHI^a, SASITARAN IYAVOO^{a,b*}

^a *University of Lincoln, Lincoln, United Kingdom.*

^b *AttoLife Limited, Norwich, United Kingdom.*

** Corresponding author at: School of Natural Sciences, University of Lincoln, Brayford Pool, Lincoln LN6 7TS, United Kingdom, siyavoo@lincoln.ac.uk.*

Abstract

The value of DNA evidence in forensic cases is substantial; however, the presence of inhibitors in biological samples can pose challenges for forensic scientists. This study aimed to assess the impact of inhibitors on forensic DNA analysis, focusing on the limitations of current DNA quantification and amplification protocols. K562 Genomic DNA was diluted to eight concentrations (100, 33, 11, 3.7, 1.23, 0.41, 0.14, and 0.05 ng/μL) and combined with two common inhibitors: haematin (in four concentrations: 2, 20, 200, and 2000 μM) and humic acid (in three concentrations: 15, 150, and 1500 ng/μL). DNA quantification was performed using the Quantifiler™ Trio DNA Quantification Kit, and amplification was carried out with the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit. Inhibition was assessed by the failure or delay of Internal Positive Control amplification, and the Degradation Index was calculated. DNA profiling effects were evaluated based on the quality of electropherograms. The results indicated that at their highest concentrations, both haematin and humic acid inhibited DNA quantification, causing either complete amplification failure or delayed IPC amplification beyond 30 threshold cycles. Samples with 1000 μM haematin showed DI values greater than 1, while 750 ng/μL of humic acid caused amplification failure of small and/or large DNA targets. The inhibitory effect increased in samples containing 16.5 and 50 ng/μL DNA combined with haematin, yet the quality of electropherograms remained unaffected. Similarly, humic acid exhibited minimal inhibitory effects, though a reduction in peak height for larger base pairs was noted at its highest concentration. In conclusion, this study highlights the significant impact of inhibitors on DNA quantification over amplification and underscores the potential inhibitory effects of high DNA concentrations.

Keywords

Forensic DNA analysis, PCR inhibitors, Quantifiler™ Trio kit, haematin, humic acid, DNA quantification.

1. Introduction

Since the first use of DNA fingerprinting for forensic DNA analysis in 1986, the field of forensic genetics has moved towards more straightforward and efficient methods. To date, the most popular DNA profiling method is Short Tandem Repeat (STR) typing. STRs are DNA loci characterised by short repetitive units of DNA that form alleles with varying lengths. These alleles are most commonly typed via Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), a technique that enables the targeted amplification of DNA fragments, followed by separation by length through capillary electrophoresis. Using this method, DNA found in biological fluids at crime scenes can be typed and compared to the DNA of suspects, providing invaluable support to criminal investigations [1].

Despite the popularity of PCR-based STR typing, this method has certain limitations. While the technique works well in the presence of pure, high-quality, and sufficient quantities of DNA, obtaining good samples is not always straightforward, given the nature of biological stains found at crime scenes. PCR is sensitive to various types of contaminants that may be present in biological matrices and the environment. These substances, known as PCR inhibitors, can interfere with different PCR components and processes, leading to suboptimal or failed amplification, even when a good quantity of non-degraded DNA is available. Common forensic PCR inhibitors include haematin found in blood, humic acid found in soil, collagen found in bones, melanin found in hair, dyes found in fabric, and certain carryover substances from DNA extraction [2-3].

In forensic genetics, PCR is not only used for STR typing but is also frequently employed for DNA quantification. Determining the amount of DNA available for STR typing is often fundamental to ensuring effective STR profiling, and one of the most effective methods for this is real-time quantitative PCR [4]. The utility of this technique in genetic testing also extends to evaluating the presence of inhibitors, allowing for the determination of whether further purification steps may be necessary before proceeding with STR typing. Inhibition can decrease the efficiency of amplification at each PCR cycle, reducing the slope of the curve in the exponential phase and delaying the cycle at which the signal surpasses the threshold

[5]. Some commercial kits, such as the Quantifiler™ Trio DNA Quantification Kit, are designed to detect inhibition through the addition of an internal positive control (IPC). The IPC is a synthetic DNA template expected to cross the threshold with a consistent threshold cycle (Ct) in non-inhibited samples. In the presence of inhibition, the IPC Ct is expected to increase. The Quantifiler™ Trio kit is also designed to detect a small autosomal (SA) and a large autosomal (LA) target in the human genome, allowing for the identification of degradation. This is because, in degraded DNA, the larger target is selectively depleted compared to the shorter target. The SA/LA ratio, referred to as the degradation index (DI), increases in more degraded samples [6].

This study aims to evaluate the effect of two common inhibitors, haematin and humic acid, on DNA quantification using the Quantifiler™ Trio kit, and amplification using the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit, a STR kit with high discrimination power and the capability of direct amplification [7]. Different levels of DNA input in combination with the contaminants are also tested to assess whether the effect of inhibitors is influenced by the availability of DNA.

2. Material studied, methods, techniques

2.1. Study samples

K562 Genomic DNA (Promega, supplied at a concentration of 400 µg/mL in TE buffer) was diluted to eight different concentrations (100, 33, 11, 3.7, 1.23, 0.41, 0.14, and 0.05 ng/µL) with deionised water. Stock solutions of haematin (Sigma-Aldrich®) and humic acid (Sigma-Aldrich®) were prepared using 1 N sodium hydroxide and deionised water [8]. Then, four concentrations of haematin (2, 20, 200, 2000 µM) and three concentrations of humic acid (15, 150, 1500 ng/µL) were separately combined with the DNA dilutions in equal volumes. Therefore, the final concentration of DNA and inhibitors in the tested samples was half of the initial concentration reported.

2.2. DNA quantification and amplification

Each sample was quantified using the Quantifiler™ Trio DNA Quantification Kit (*Applied Biosystems*™), following the manufacturer's recommendations. The same samples were amplified using the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit (*Applied Biosystems*™), adhering to a reduced volume protocol [7]. All samples were processed in triplicates.

2.3. Data analysis

The effect of inhibition was evaluated by reviewing the Quantifiler™ Trio IPC Ct values. The DI was also calculated as the ratio between the concentrations of the SA and LA targets. The results were compared with the data reported in the Quantifiler™ Trio validation study [6]. The inhibitory effects on STR typing with the VeriFiler™ Express kit were determined based on the quality of the obtained electropherograms.

3. Results

As shown in Table 1 and 2, both haematin and humic acid, at their highest concentrations, either prevented amplification or delayed the IPC Ct values beyond 30. Higher IPC Ct values were also observed in association with high DNA concentrations: 16.5 and 50 ng/μL of DNA combined with any amount of haematin resulted in IPC values close to or exceeding 30, similar to the results obtained when combining 50 ng/μL of DNA with any concentration of humic acid.

A DI higher than 1 was observed in samples containing 1000 μM of haematin. For samples containing 750 ng/μL of humic acid, the DI was undetermined due to the amplification failure of the SA and/or LA targets.

The results from DNA quantification did not correspond to those observed in STR typing. The quality of the electropherograms remained unaffected by haematin at any concentration, irrespective of the DNA quantity. In contrast, limited inhibitory effects were seen when typing samples containing humic acid, although a reduction in peak heights for larger base pairs was noted at the highest concentration.

Table 1. Average degradation index (DI) and internal positive control (IPC) threshold cycle (Ct) values obtained from Quantifiler™ Trio quantification of the triplicate study samples, determined by a combination of DNA and haematin at the indicated final sample concentrations. Where one of the triplicate samples had an undetermined DI, the average DI value is indicated with a '>' sign before the highest DI value, as the undetermined value would be even higher.

DNA concentration (ng/μL)	Haematin concentration (μM)	DI	IPC Ct
0.025	0	0.68	29.64
	1	0.59	29.74
	10	0.57	29.64
	100	0.49	29.95
	1000	>21	30.60
0.07	0	0.47	29.69
	1	0.52	29.69
	10	0.55	29.70
	100	0.59	29.84
	1000	>9	30.91
0.205	0	0.53	29.49
	1	0.58	29.44
	10	0.58	29.64
	100	0.52	29.68
	1000	4.88	31.16
0.615	0	0.52	29.49
	1	0.48	29.44
	10	0.47	29.32
	100	0.50	29.55
	1000	58.65	35.07
1.85	0	0.57	29.41
	1	0.53	29.30
	10	0.57	29.38
	100	0.57	29.68
	1000	1.70	34.50

5.5	0	0.55	29.53
	1	0.53	29.53
	10	0.56	29.75
	100	0.52	29.78
	1000	3.17	Undetermined
16.5	0	0.59	29.90
	1	0.59	29.96
	10	0.57	30.12
	100	0.54	30.20
	1000	1.88	Undetermined
50	0	0.68	30.34
	1	0.64	30.25
	10	0.64	30.43
	100	0.57	30.57
	1000	2.78	Undetermined

Table 2. Average degradation index (DI) and internal positive control (IPC) threshold cycle (Ct) values obtained from Quantifiler™ Trio quantification of the triplicate study samples, determined by a combination of DNA and humic acid at the indicated final sample concentrations.

DNA concentration (ng/μL)	Humic Acid concentration (ng/μL)	DI	IPC Ct
0.025	0	0.26	29.11
	7.5	0.41	28.93
	75	0.51	28.59
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
0.07	0	0.50	28.58
	7.5	0.55	28.53
	75	0.51	28.57
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
0.205	0	0.51	28.44
	7.5	0.75	28.03
	75	0.39	28.32
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined

0.615	0	0.52	28.29
	7.5	0.65	28.12
	75	0.56	28.11
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
1.85	0	0.66	28.03
	7.5	0.71	27.89
	75	0.56	28.29
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
5.5	0	0.79	28.40
	7.5	0.71	28.48
	75	0.53	28.70
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
16.5	0	0.71	28.90
	7.5	0.70	28.91
	75	0.57	29.29
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined
50	0	0.79	29.27
	7.5	0.68	29.45
	75	0.59	30.07
	750	Undetermined	Undetermined

4. Discussion

The results obtained from the real-time PCR quantification were comparable to the data reported in the Quantifiler™ Trio validation study [6]. In that study, haematin concentrations of 200 to 1250 μM were used, showing delayed IPC values and amplification failure of SA and/or LA targets starting from 750 μM . In the present study, a gap was present between 100 to 1000 μM of haematin, with similar challenges observed at 1000 μM and acceptable results at 100 μM . Likewise, in the validation study, humic acid concentrations of 200 to 800 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$ were used, with issues starting from 400 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$. The present study showed comparable results when using 750 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$, and minimal effects with the second highest concentration of 75 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$. Another study produced similar results using different real-time PCR-based quantification kits [9].

This study, therefore, confirmed previous observations, including high DI values being linked to inhibition rather than DNA degradation, as good quality

control DNA was used. Additionally, this investigation revealed increased inhibition associated with higher DNA amounts in the sample. In fact, excessive amounts of DNA are considered a PCR inhibitor, leading to poor DNA amplification, primarily due to physical obstructions [10]. It is perhaps not surprising to observe increased inhibition in the samples analysed in this study, where a combination of high inhibitor concentrations and high DNA amounts was present.

Although inhibitory effects were observed during DNA quantification, this study reported very little effect on the STR typing results. This suggests an enhanced resilience to inhibitors in the VeriFiler™ Express kit compared to the Quantifiler™ Trio kit. A separate study also demonstrated limited inhibitory effects of haematin (250 to 750 µM) and humic acid (100 to 300 ng/µL) when using four other forensic STR kits [11].

Future investigations may be required to fully understand the effects of inhibitors on PCR for both DNA quantification and amplification, including increasing the number of samples, adding more inhibitor data points, and testing a wider range of inhibitor types.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated the effects of different concentrations of haematin and humic acid on real-time PCR quantification using Quantifiler™ Trio kit and STR typing using the VeriFiler™ Express kit, highlighting a greater impact on forensic DNA quantification than on amplification. The inhibitory effect of high DNA concentrations in combination with elevated levels of contaminants was also emphasised. However, further studies are required to expand our understanding of inhibition and to work towards improving quantification and amplification methods.

6. Conflict of interest statement

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of their affiliated company or organisation.

7. References

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